

Fluorescent dye transport assay for SLC7A3 using HEK JumpIn SLC7A3 OE cells

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Assay description

Purpose of the assay is to determine the functionality of the SLC7A3 transporter, stably expressed in the HEK-293 JumpIn TReX cell line (SLC7A3 OverExpressing - OE - cell line). SLC7A3 (CAT-3) mediates the entry of L-type cationic amino acids (i.e., L-Arginine, L-Ornithine and L-Lysine) into neurons. The transport mediated by SLC7A3 is therefore electrogenic. For this reason, the HEK-293 JumpIn TReX/SLC7A3 OE cell line was tested using the Membrane Potential (MP) dye read-out, which is described in the section below.

Assay protocol

FLIPR Membrane Potential (MP) dye is a lipophilic, anionic, bis-oxonol dye from Molecular Devices, able to cross the plasma membrane and to measure voltage changes by its potential-dependent accumulation and redistribution. When cells are depolarized, the dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence. This read-out is compatible with high-throughput applications. A general protocol for the use of MP dye requires to discard cell medium and load the cells with the dye dissolved in a suitable buffer for a period that typically ranges from 10-15 minutes to 1 hour. Then the dye has to be excited with the proper wavelength and the emission is acquired. Detection of fluorescent emission is achieved by means of a fluorescent plate reader (such as FLIPR^{TETRA} or Hamamatsu FDSS), able to excite the probe and to read its emission.

The specific protocol that was used for the HEK-293 JumpIn TReX/SLC7A3 OE cell line is reported below in details:

- Cell lines: HEK293 JumpIn TReX/SLC7A3 OE; HEK293 JumpIn TReX WT (used as control)
- Cells seeding: 10.000 c/w in 384-well plates (black, clear bottom, poly-Lys coated). Induction was carried out adding 1 µg/mL Doxycycline during seeding procedure (24h adhesion)
- Read-out: MP dye
- Dye loading: after medium manual discard, cells were loaded with 20 µL/w of MP dye (1X) dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer (Tyrode's Buffer: 130 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 2 mM CaCl₂, 5 mM NaHCO₃, 1 mM MgCl₂, 20 mM HEPES, pH 7.4) and incubated for 30 min at RT
- Substrates' injection: after incubation with MP dye, substrates were injected (10 µL/w, 3X) using FLIPR^{TETRA} plate reader and fluorescence was recorded by the instrument for 5 min using the following Excitation/Emission filters: exc. 510-545 nm, em. 565-625 nm. The substrates used were L-Arginine, L-Ornithine and L-Lysine. All the stimuli were dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer and injected at different concentrations, to determine the dose-dependency of the SLC7A3 response (for each substrate, top concentration started from 1 mM, and was followed by a 1:2 dilution step)
- Data Export: FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates (quadruplicates) were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained as raw data by applying the "subtract bias based on samples" correction at a reading step before injection. Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC) signal for the entire kinetic after the injection. Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves with GraphPad PRISM software.

Additional information

Not available

Target data

SLC	SLC7A3
Synonyms	CAT-3 (Cationic Amino Acid Transporter)
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 7
UniProt ID	Identifier: Q8WY07-1
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE02KK-T (HEK-SLC7A3-WTOE-p1)

Assay data

Compound name (1)	L-Arginine
PubChem CID	6322
Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma cat: A5006
Mode of action	Substrate
Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC50= 283 μ M
Compound name (2)	L-Ornithine hydrochloride
PubChem CID	76654
Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma cat. W419001
Mode of action	Substrate
Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC50= 237 μ M
Compound name (3)	L-Lysine
PubChem CID	5962
Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma cat: L5501
Mode of action	Substrate
Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC50= 158 μ M

Discussion

A strong, dose-dependent and specific increase of the fluorescent signal (due to influx of charged amino acids into the cells) was detected upon injection of L-Arginine, L-Ornithine and L-Lysine, after induction of target expression with Doxycycline for 24h. This cell-based assay was therefore functionally validated using MP dye as read-out.

<http://re-solute.eu>

Cross references

- *RESOLUTE* report at [Zenodo](#).